

Studies on Complexes of Copper(II) Alkanoates with 2-, 3- and 4-Aminopyridines

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2-, 3- and 4-Aminopyridines yield mono- and bis-amine complexes on interaction with copper(II) acetate, propionate, n-butyrate and isobutyrate. The complexes are solid, stable and are green or blue-violet in colour. Conductance, magnetic moments, electronic and ir spectral studies reveal that they are neutral six-coordinate species having a distorted octahedral geometry except bis-amine complex of 4-aminopyridine with copper butyrate which has a square-planar configuration.

Pyridine and its various substituted derivatives as well as related ligands like quinoline, isoquinoline and morpholine, form a variety of complexes with copper(II) alkanoates. However, no work has been reported on their complexes with aminopyridines. At the same time a little is known about the behaviour of aminopyridines as coordinating ligands which have two donor sites—pyridine nitrogen and amino nitrogen. They may function as monodentate or bidentate using either one or both of the N atoms in them. Consequently, a number of their complexes with copper(II) alkanoates derived from acetic, propionic acid and n- and isobutyric acids have been synthesized in an attempt to ascertain whether the mode of coordination of the ligands in these complexes is monodentate, ligating through pyridine ring nitrogen or amino nitrogen atom, or bidentate utilising both of the nitrogen atoms.

Results and Discussion

The 1 : 1 complexes were green while 1 : 2 complexes were either blue or violet (Table 1). All the complexes are stable in air and fairly soluble in polar organic solvents. Their molar conductance values (Table 1) show that the complexes are neutral and covalent in character¹.

Magnetic studies : The 1 : 1 complexes of copper(II) acetate, propionate, n-butyrate and isobutyrate with 2-ampy and 3-ampy with copper(II) acetate and n-butyrate possess subnormal magnetic moments (Table 1) and have been assigned a dimeric syn-syn carboxylate bridged structure^{2,3}. All of the bis-ampy complexes exhibit magnetic moments in the range 1.77–1.97 B.M. showing that these complexes may not have a tetrahedral structure^{2,4}. Hence, they have been regarded as mononuclear species possessing either a square-planar or a distorted octahedral stereochemistry containing monodentate or bidentate chelating carboxylate groups.

Electronic spectra : The 1 : 1 complexes of 2- and 3-ampy exhibit only one broad band in

688–712 nm region which is a characteristic of distorted octahedral Cu^{II} complexes and is assigned to $d_{xz}, d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions⁵. This band suggests that the complexes have a monomeric structure while magnetic moment studies indicate a dimeric structure for them making it apparent that 1 : 1 dimeric complexes in methanol change to monomeric species as a result of solvent coordination⁶. To clarify this further, diffuse reflectance spectra of Cu(acetate)₂·2-ampy and Cu(n-butyrate)₂·3-ampy were recorded. In these spectra an additional band appeared as a shoulder at 375 nm which is considered a characteristic of dimeric structure⁷. These investigations led to the conclusion that the 1 : 1 complexes in solid phase have dimeric carboxylate bridged distorted octahedral structure similar to that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate^{2,3}.

The 1 : 2 complexes in methanol exhibit one broad band around 664–692 nm indicating a distorted octahedral environment around copper(II) ion. In the diffuse reflectance spectra of the 4-ampy complexes with copper(II) acetate and propionate one strong band appears at 575 and 600 nm respectively analogous to the band observed around 600 nm in distorted octahedral complexes of aliphatic diamines with various copper(II) salts⁸. However, the complex of 4-ampy with copper(II) n-butyrate shows a band at 534 nm pointing the complex to be of square-planar disposition^{9,10} in which the carboxylate group functions as a monodentate ligand. In solution it exists as a six-coordinated distorted octahedral complex. The increase in coordination number from 4 to 6 in solution could result either by solvent participation or by change of the pattern of coordination of the carboxylate from monodentate to bidentate chelation.

Infrared spectra : The NH stretching frequencies in all the 1 : 1 complexes fall around 3 340–3 458 and 3 208–3 330 cm⁻¹ while in all the 1 : 2 complexes these occur around 3 325–3 350 and 3 175–3 210 cm⁻¹. These frequencies show a small positive shift of 8–28 cm⁻¹ which rules out the

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Molar cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
	Cu	C	H		
1 : 1 Complexes					
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (Light green)	23.06 (23.00)	39.00 (39.20)	4.27 (4.35)	21.12	1.62
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot 2\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (Green)	20.62 (20.92)	43.35 (43.49)	5.20 (5.27)	15.83	1.43*
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_3\text{H}_7\text{-n})_2 \cdot 2\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (Green)	18.88 (19.15)	46.98 (47.05)	5.90 (6.03)	14.38	1.36
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_2\text{H}_5\text{-iso})_2 \cdot 2\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (Green)	19.95 (19.15)	46.83 (47.05)	5.98 (6.03)	10.26	1.44
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (Light green)	22.85 (23.00)	39.08 (39.20)	4.25 (4.35)	17.31	1.49
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_3\text{H}_7\text{-n})_2 \cdot 3\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (Light green)	18.88 (19.15)	46.87 (47.05)	6.00 (6.03)	59.98	1.53
1 : 2 Complexes					
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2 \cdot (2\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Blue)	16.94 (17.18)	45.37 (45.46)	4.77 (4.87)	20.47	1.97*
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot (2\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Greenish blue)	15.75 (15.97)	48.25 (48.30)	5.48 (5.53)	16.48	1.85*
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_3\text{H}_7\text{-n})_2 \cdot (2\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Blue)	14.76 (14.92)	50.59 (50.76)	6.07 (6.11)	18.10	1.88
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_2\text{H}_5\text{-iso})_2 \cdot (2\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Light blue)	14.70 (14.92)	50.58 (50.76)	6.08 (6.11)	15.67	1.84
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2 \cdot (3\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Greenish)	16.95 (17.18)	45.36 (45.46)	4.82 (4.57)	18.47	1.91
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot (3\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Brownish violet)	15.75 (15.97)	48.11 (48.30)	5.47 (5.53)	16.33	1.80
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_3\text{H}_7\text{-n})_2 \cdot (3\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Brownish violet)	14.75 (14.92)	50.65 (50.76)	6.06 (6.11)	13.38	1.92
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_2\text{H}_5\text{-iso})_2 \cdot (3\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Brownish violet)	14.62 (14.92)	50.65 (50.76)	6.05 (6.11)	15.85	1.80
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2 \cdot (4\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Blue)	16.88 (17.18)	45.16 (45.46)	5.05 (4.87)	71.16	1.83
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot (4\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Blue)	15.70 (15.97)	48.05 (48.30)	5.38 (5.53)	46.53	1.77
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_3\text{H}_7\text{-n})_2 \cdot (4\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Violet)	14.70 (14.92)	50.71 (50.76)	6.10 (6.11)	51.85	1.82
$\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_2\text{H}_5\text{-iso})_2 \cdot (4\text{-NH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ (Violet)	14.90 (14.92)	50.69 (50.76)	6.08 (6.11)	59.13	1.87

*At 293 K.

possibility of interaction of amine group nitrogen with Cu^{II} ion and suggest that the aminopyridine ligands coordinate to the Cu^{II} ion through the ring nitrogen atom.

All of the 1 : 1 adducts of copper(II) alkanates with aminopyridines show an intense sharp band due to COO stretch at a higher frequency in the range of $1605\text{--}1640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as compared to the asymmetric stretching band observed in the region $1588\text{--}1605 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in their corresponding parent Cu^{II} alkanates. This higher shift indicates coordination of the aminopyridine to the Cu^{II} ion. The bands in the region $1420\text{--}1440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to symmetric carboxyl stretching frequencies. The separation of the two carboxyl stretching frequencies fall in the range $200\text{--}225 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is greater than the value reported for the corresponding non-adduct copper(II) alkanates with heterocyclic amines^{11,12}. Further, in comparison to sodium propionate the directions of the shifts in both of the frequencies, viz. ν_{COO} (asym) and ν_{CN} (sym) in copper(II) propionate and $\text{Cu}(\text{propionate})_2 \cdot (2\text{-ampy})$

($1605, 1430 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) complex are towards higher wave numbers which is characteristic of complexes having bridging bidentate carboxylate groups¹³. Hence, IR and magnetic moment studies reveal that the 1 : 1 complexes are binuclear carboxylate bridged species. In all the 1 : 2 adducts the ν_{COO} (asy) and ν_{COO} (sym) are observed as two strong peaks in the region $1605\text{--}1640$ and $1400\text{--}1440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, thereby making the differences in the frequencies in these complexes to fall in the range $180\text{--}220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This shows that in the 1 : 2 complexes the carboxylate group behaves as a bidentate chelating group and the complexes possess a distorted octahedral geometry as proposed by electronic spectral studies. However, the square-planar structure of $\text{Cu}(\text{n-butylate})_2 \cdot (4\text{-ampy})_2$ proposed on the basis of its electronic spectra is not in agreement with the results obtained from COO frequency difference data. Since Δ -values have not been considered a very reliable criterion for deciding the mode of bonding of a carboxylate group¹⁴, and the possibility of the carboxylate group being monodentate in this complex is not ruled out.

A comparison of the far-infrared spectra of the complexes of ampys with those of the corresponding parent copper(II) carboxylate and ampy ligand does indeed show the presence of additional bands in the spectra of the complexes in the regions 380–320 and 290–240 cm^{-1} . These frequencies are tentatively assigned to Cu–O and Cu–N stretching frequencies respectively.

In conclusion, all of the 1 : 1 complexes are dimeric syn-syn carboxylate bridged species while the 1 : 2 complexes are monomeric and six-coordinate species of distorted octahedral geometry except bis(n-butyrate)bis(4-ampy)copper(II) which may be regarded as a square-planar entity.

Experimental

Basic copper(II) carbonate, $\text{CuCO}_3 \cdot \text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H.) was purified by washing with hot water. Copper(II) acetate monohydrate (AnalaR), propionic acid (Riedel), n-butyric acid (B.D.H.), isobutyric acid (B.D.H.), and the ligands, 2-ampy (B.D.H.), 3-ampy (Fluka, A.G.) and 4-ampy (Merck) were used as such. Copper(II) alkanoates were prepared by the direct interaction of basic copper(II) carbonate or copper(II) acetate with the appropriate acid in aqueous or alcoholic medium and subsequent manipulation of reaction mixture.

Addition complexes of copper(II) alkanoates : The addition complexes with 2-, 3- and 4-ampys were prepared by their interaction with the respective copper(II) alkanoate dissolved in acetone or methanol in 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting mixture on concentration and cooling deposited a green or blue/violet coloured solid in each case which was

washed with acetone and dried under reduced pressure.

Copper was estimated gravimetrically as cuprous thiocyanate. C and H contents were estimated micro-analytically. Molar conductance was determined in methanol using a Systronics 303 conductivity meter. Magnetic moment was determined at room temperature (293 K) by Gouy's method. Absorption spectra (MeOH) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 8-100 spectrophotometer, diffuse reflectance spectra on a Carl-Zeiss DMR-21 spectrophotometer, near-ir spectra at R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Madras, and ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 597 spectrophotometer.

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